

Climate change is moving faster than we are. If we want to turn the tide, we will have to speed up.

Climate change is here to stay, so we'd better prepare for it

By KOEN DE BOSSCHERE

Over the past decade, we have begun to understand what climate change really means for the world. We have discovered that it is not limited to melting ice caps in the mountains and on the poles, or rising sea levels in coastal areas, but that it also impacts our backyard. There are more days with extreme temperatures; in some areas, there are huge wildfires, or severe flooding. Due to lower crop yields, food prices are rising, pushing up the cost of living.

As temperatures continue to rise in the coming decades, the climate will continue to change, and we will have to adapt to this new normal. In order to do so, we will need technology to monitor and control strategic processes and services that are at the foundation of our modern society (power grids, water supply, food production, ...).

Key insights

- Climate change affects all regions of the world, including the industrialized world, in ways that most people did not anticipate.
- To safeguard our modern society, we will have to adapt and to become more resilient by preparing for wildfires, mega-droughts, flooding, ...
- To slow down climate change, we will have to stop using fossil fuels. Defossilizing the global economy will require major investment in digital technologies. The internet of things (IoT), edge and cloud computing can play a major role in adapting to climate change.

Key recommendations

- We should invest in digital solutions that will help defossilize the economy: smart grids, smart mobility, smart cities, further dematerialization, ...
- Europe should invest in the IoT, edge and cloud computing as key digital technologies for the European Green Deal.

According to [1], the term “sustainability” was introduced in the 18th century in the context of forestry. At that time, it referred to managing forests to ensure that future generations had access to enough wood for fuel and for timber. In the 20th century it was broadened beyond forests. The first report of the club of Rome, “The Limits to Growth” [2], made very clear that exponential growth of resource consumption could not be sustainable on a finite planet, and that one day natural resources would be depleted. The same report already warned about the exponential increase of CO₂ in the atmosphere in 1972. Later, the definition of sustainability was broadened with social and economic aspects into the formulation of the “triple bottom line”

consisting of people, planet and profit [3]. Today's best-known definition of sustainability are the 17 sustainable development goals defined by the United Nations in 2015 [4].

Climate change

Over the past decade, it has become apparent that climate change is increasingly impacting the planet, society and the economy, and that slowing down and eventually stopping or even reversing climate change is probably the biggest challenge of the next 50 years. The UN Secretary-General António Guterres already warned the world in 2018 that “Climate change is moving faster than we are”; since then, carbon emissions have only increased.

As of today, in many countries, evolution rather than revolution is considered the appropriate approach for fighting climate change, but evolution takes time. In addition, many countries require solutions to be affordable in order to be politically realistic. The fact that doing too little or acting too late could in the end be more expensive is not the first concern. In 2022, the United Nations climate change conference COP27 agreed on a loss and damage fund for vulnerable countries hit hard by climate disasters but excluded any mention of winding down the use of fossil fuels [5]. This is a clear sign that countries find it easier to pay for the consequences of climate change than to tackle the root cause.

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While there are still people unsure about the causes of global warming (manmade or part of natural fluctuations in the climate), there is a growing awareness that climate

change is real, that we will definitely have to adapt, and we will have to do it fast because the climate is changing faster than we could have imagined a decade ago.

Another recent insight is that climate change impacts all parts of the world, not just small islands in the Pacific or poor countries, but also the industrialized world. Hence, while some will be much worse affected than others, everybody on the planet is going to pay the price, be it directly (fires, flood, heat, drought, ...) or indirectly (higher cost of living, broken value chains, higher insurance premiums, contributions to the loss and damage fund, ...).

According to a study released by the First Street Foundation [6], in 2053, 107 million Americans will experience at least one day of $>51^{\circ}\text{C}$ (125°F) per year, compared to 8 million today; see Figure 1. All over the US, the number of extremely hot days will increase from one week to one month. Some US citizens might decide to leave the hot areas and move to areas with more moderate temperatures where living is more affordable (lower heating and cooling costs). This will have an impact on the local economy of the states involved.

Economic consequences

The examples are plentiful, and they all illustrate how a mild increase of the average temperature can have serious economic consequences.

Lake Mead, the largest freshwater reservoir of the US, providing water and electric power to 40 million people living in the desert, was in the summer of 2022 at 27% of its full capacity (this is the lowest level since 1937 when the lake was filling up for the first time). It took seven years to fill up the lake, and the last year that it was completely full was in the summer of 1999; see Figure 1 [8].

The water level in the lake is nearing the level where the Hoover Dam will stop producing electricity (950 ft) [9]. In 2020, electricity production was about a third of the maximum capability with a full lake.

Moreover, in 2023, Arizona will receive 25% less water from the Colorado river. This means the end of hundreds of desert farms that depend on the irrigation water from the Colorado river. Some will survive on pumped up ground water, but since it

Figure 1: US counties with at least one day of 51°C per year, from [7]

Figure 2: Lake Mead water levels [8]. Power generation halts at 950 ft. The dam stops functioning at 895 ft.

rains very little in the desert (and most rain runs off or evaporates), this water resource will eventually get depleted too. California is a major producer (and exporter) of agricultural products. Without irrigation, the productivity of the whole area will shrink and farmers might have to switch to crops that depend less on water. Food prices will increase, and given the US' role as an exporter, this will have consequences beyond national borders.

The Colorado river is not the only case. The Mississippi river was at its lowest level in a century in October 2022. In some places, the river could be crossed on foot [10], while seawater entered its estuary, threatening the collection of drinking water in Louisiana [11]. The Mississippi is one of the major transportation arteries of the US used to transport crops from the central US. If the megadrought of 2022 becomes the “new normal”, this will have serious consequences for the states that depend on the river for transportation, drinking water and irrigation.

The Yangtze River, the largest and most important waterway in China, was 40% lower than normal in August 2022. 84 million people depend on the hydropower generated by the Three Gorges dam on the Yangtze River. Major companies in the area like Toyota and Foxconn and a major vehicle battery maker had to suspend their operations in August 2022 to save energy. This will impact China's GDP in 2022. The lack of precipitation is also threatening crops all over the area [12].

In Europe, the River Po carried 10% of its usual flow in the summer of 2022, and the Po Valley, the food basket of Italy (with 30-40% of the country's total agricultural production), ran out of irrigation water, leading to a substantially lower yield (e.g. 60% less risotto rice).

Extreme drought is not only a problem for food production, but also for livestock farming. As an example, some farms in the US have had to sell cattle because of increasing feed prices, low-quality or insufficient forage [13]. This led to a reduction in the supply of dairy products. Vineyards

are also suffering from drought, extreme heat and fires [14].

As mentioned above, major transportation arteries in Europe and the US (the Rhine and Danube rivers and the Mississippi) reached such low levels in 2022 that barges could only be loaded up to 25%, leading to delays and fivefold transportation costs. This has a severe impact on industry (and will cost an estimated 0.2 points of economic growth in Germany).

Rivers also provide cooling water for fossil and nuclear power plants to condense the used steam back to water. When the flow of the river is too low (or when the water gets too hot), the plants have to reduce the power production, or to shut down. In the worst case, this leads to suspended operations in energy-intensive factories too. This is perfect storm: a megadrought leads to less precipitation and hydropower, and problems with the operation of large thermoelectric power plants, all while during a time of peak water and electricity consumption.

Ecological consequences

Global warming does not only impact people and livestock; severe drought obviously also impacts natural ecosystems. Animals cannot survive in the wild without water and food. In places where water disappears, wild animals die. In some parts of Africa, more large animals were killed by the drought and wildfires than by poaching in 2022. This poses a major challenge for nature conservation.

Due to the changing climate, natural ecosystems are changing across the world, and some species will have to adapt in order to survive. In any case, climate change is going to impact biodiversity because the climate is changing faster than the biological capacity of species to adapt to the new situation [15]. Since humans are part of and depend on the natural ecosystem too, some global areas might become too harsh (or too expensive) for us to thrive too.

Climate change and biodiversity are intimately connected: climate change will impact biodiversity, while protecting biodiversity might also slow down climate change. An example is the protection of (tropical) forests and wetlands. Since they

Figure 3: Climate change and loss of biodiversity are connected in a positive feedback loop

	Asia	Europe	N-America	World	Asia/Europe/N-America
Potatoes	178,52	107,69	24,09	359,07	86%
Corn	373,81	365,31	123,94	1160	74%
Rice	676,61	10,32	4,07	756,74	91%
Wheat	347,89	255,02	84,87	760,93	90%

Table 1: Staple food production around the world (2020) [17]

Illegally abandoned tyres in the River Po visible due to drought. Carmagnola, Italy, July 2022. Source: Mike Dot on Adobe Stock

soak up CO₂, they slow down climate change. Should they disappear, huge amounts of CO₂ will be released, further accelerating climate change. Such positive feedback loops are dangerous mechanisms, and once activated, they are extremely hard to stop [16]; see Figure 3. Hence protecting biodiversity is a very important priority in efforts to control climate change.

Given the recent weather evolutions, weather in moderate climate zones seems to be becoming less moderate: longer periods of drought, heavier rainfall and floods, more violent storms, higher temperatures (both on average and at the extremes). The northern hemisphere contains 67% of the land of the planet, and almost 90% of the population. It also produces the staple foods for a large part of the world as shown in Table 1.

If food production decreases by, for example, 20% by the changed climate in the coming years (without taking into account the effects of wars), this will lead to increased food prices. Since the food market is a global market, the increased prices will be felt all over world, including in areas where climate change has a milder impact. In poor areas of the world, this will lead to famine.

This effect will be aggravated by the growing world population which will require 50% more food by 2050 (a considerable part to feed farm animals). Hence, before anything else, climate change is creating a food security challenge for the world. Hunger inevitably leads to social unrest, and political instability. This might destabilize some countries.

Technical solutions for the food security challenge include new crops that are better adapted to the new climate, vertical farms in urban areas, lab meat, and reducing food waste in the food supply chain; lifestyle changes include consuming food with a smaller ecological footprint, like vegetarian alternatives to meat.

The way forward

Since we cannot stop climate change in the short term, we will have to adapt. In fact, we will need two types of adaptation: (i) adaptations to decarbonize the world to slow down climate change, and (ii) adaptations to deal with the existing consequences of climate change.

Given the size of the problem, there are no easy fixes to deal with climate change, and business as usual will not suffice. Adaptations to decarbonize the world will require investment, and lifestyle changes. Some recent studies indicate that 2050 for

net zero will be too late to limit climate change to 1.5°C, and that the world should try to reach net zero sooner. Many major corporations have announced plans to work towards net zero in 2040.

Digital technologies will play a crucial role in facilitating lifestyle changes and adapting to climate change.

- Decarbonizing the world will require advanced digital technologies to design a new power grid, merge and balance renewable sources of energy, storage systems, distributed power generation, ...
- Lifestyle changes will be facilitated by digital technologies too. Video conferences are in some cases a good alternative for in-person business meetings, immersive virtual experiences might in some cases be a low-carbon alternative to travel.
- Finally, there are adaptations to climate change. Advanced sensing technologies can help monitor extreme weather conditions, precision agriculture can help increase the yield of crops, genetically modified crops could be made more resistant to extreme weather conditions, a digital twin of planet earth can help predict the effects of climate change.

These digital systems will be geographically distributed, connected, cognitive, and the size of whole countries. The key digital technology used to design and build them

will be the IoT, edge and cloud computing. Europe should invest in these technologies in order to secure itself a place in the global market of climate change adaptation technologies.

Conclusion

Climate change is real, and it will not go away, so we will have to adapt. Digital technologies are one of the key technologies that will help humanity to adapt to the new climate normal. The biggest challenge is to decarbonize the world as fast as we can. This will require huge investment in power savings, and new power-generation and power-transportation systems. All these solutions will require lots of for digital technologies based on the IoT, edge and cloud computing. Europe should invest in these technologies to order to stay at the forefront of climate change adaptation technologies.

References

- [1] U. Grober, "Deep roots – A conceptual history of 'sustainable development' (Nachhaltigkeit)," 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://bibliothek.wzb.eu/pdf/2007/p07-002.pdf>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [2] D.H. Meadows et al. , "The Limits to Growth," Club of Rome, 2 March 1972. [Online]. Available: <https://www.clubofrome.org/publication/the-limits-to-growth/>.
- [3] "Triple bottom line," The Economist, 17 November 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://www.economist.com/news/2009/11/17/triple-bottom-line>. [Accessed 26 November 2022].
- [4] "The 17 Goals," United Nations, [Online]. Available: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> . [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [5] "COP27 ends with announcement of historic loss and damage fund," United Nations, 22 November 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/cop27-ends-announcement-historic-loss-and-damage-fund>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [6] T. Grant, "Millions of people in Midwest to experience 'extreme heat belt' by 2053: Report," ABC News, 16 August 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://abcnews.go.com/US/millions-people-midwest-experience-extreme-heat-belt-2053/story?id=88410076>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [7] "The 6th National Climate Risk Assessment: Hazardous Heat," First Street Foundation, 15 August 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://report.firststreet.org/heat>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [8] "Lake Mead Keeps Dropping," NASA , [Online]. Available: <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/images/150111/lake-mead-keeps-dropping>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [9] R. Ramirez, "The West's historic drought is threatening hydropower at Hoover Dam," CNN, 16 August 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://edition.cnn.com/2022/08/16/us/hoover-dam-hydropower-drought-climate/index.html>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].

- [10] A. Chinchar, B. Miller and D. Alsup, "The mighty Mississippi is so low, people are walking to a unique rock formation rarely accessible by foot," CNN, 16 October 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://edition.cnn.com/2022/10/15/weather/mississippi-river-low-water-tower-rock-climate/index.html>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [11] R. Rojas, "As Drought Drops Water Level in the Mississippi, Shipwrecks Surface and Worries Rise," The New York Times, 3 November 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/11/03/us/mississippi-river-drought.html>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [12] H. Davidson, "China drought causes Yangtze to dry up, sparking shortage of hydropower," The Guardian, 22 August 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2022/aug/22/china-drought-causes-yangtze-river-to-dry-up-sparking-shortage-of-hydropower>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [13] "New AFBF Survey Shows Drought's Increasing Toll on Farmers and Ranchers," 14 August 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fb.org/market-intel/new-afbf-survey-shows-droughts-increasing-toll-on-farmers-and-ranchers>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [14] M. Scott, "Hard-hit by climate change, winemakers turn to sustainability to ride the storms," Reuters, 14 September 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.reuters.com/business/sustainable-business/hard-hit-by-climate-change-winemakers-turn-sustainability-ride-storms-2022-09-14/>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [15] I. Quintero et al. , "Rates of projected climate change dramatically exceed past rates of climatic niche evolution among vertebrate species," Ecology Letters, vol. 16, no. 8, pp. 1095-1103, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12144>, 2013.
- [16] I. B. Ruiz, "Five worst climate feedback loops," Deutsche Welle, 5 April 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.dw.com/en/when-nature-harms-itself-five-scary-climate-feedback-loops/a-43649814>. [Accessed 27 November 2022].
- [17] Govind Bhutada, "Mapped: Food Production Around the World," 12 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/cp/mapped-food-production-around-the-world/>.

Koen De Bosschere is a professor in the electronics department of Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium.

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